

Event title	WORKSHOP: Hybrid de novo genome assembly
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	07/10/2021
Time of event	2-5pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>It's now easier than ever to assemble new reference genomes thanks to hybrid genome assembly approaches which enable research on organisms for which reference genomes were not previously available. These approaches combine the strengths of short (Illumina) and long (PacBio or Nanopore) read technologies, resulting in improved assembly quality.</p> <p>In this workshop we will learn how to create and assess genome assemblies from Illumina and Nanopore reads using data from a <i>Bacillus Subtilis</i> strain. We will demonstrate two hybrid-assembly methods using the tools Flye, Pilon, and Unicycler to perform assembly and subsequent error correction. You will learn how to visualise input read sets and the assemblies produced at each stage and assess the quality of the final assembly.</p> <p>All analyses will be performed using Galaxy Australia, an online platform for biological research that allows people to use computational data analysis tools and workflows without the need for programming experience.</p> <p>This workshop is presented by the Australian BioCommons and Melbourne Bioinformatics with the assistance of a network of facilitators from the national Bioinformatics Training Cooperative.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom as described in https://zenodo.org/record/4158583</p> <p>Grace Hall led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants then moved into breakout rooms where they had the chance to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>The workshop followed the tutorial linked in the 'Related work' section.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule.</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/hybrid-assembly
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	International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Galaxy Australia Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945 Workflows http://edamontology.org/topic_0769 Genomics http://edamontology.org/topic_0622 Genome assembly http://edamontology.org/operation_0525 De novo assembly http://edamontology.org/operation_0524
Contact	Melissa Burke (melissa@biocommons.org.au)
Audience	This workshop is for Australian researchers who are performing or will perform hybrid genome assembly as part of their projects.
Prerequisites	To get the most out of the workshops you must have experience with the basics of using Galaxy Australia such as setting up a history, uploading data and running tools. It is recommended that you complete the tutorial Galaxy 101 for Everyone . No programming experience is required.
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Galaxy Australia account • This workshop was run using Galaxy version 21.01 and made use of access to Galaxy Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS). • Slack was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom.
Learning outcomes	By the end of this workshop you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe how Nanopore and Illumina reads can be used together to produce a high quality assembly • Use genome assembly and polishing programs in Galaxy Australia • Assess the quality of a genome assembly with and without a reference genome • Assemble an unknown, previously undocumented genome to high-quality using Nanopore and Illumina reads <p>The workshop will NOT provide an introduction to the basics of Galaxy. If you would like to learn about this topic there are several tutorials available via the Galaxy Training Network.</p>
Lead Trainer	Ms Grace Hall, Melbourne Bioinformatics
Facilitators	Mr Steven Morgan, Melbourne Bioinformatics Dr Igor Makunin, QCIF Bioinformatics

Related work

This workshop follows the tutorial 'Hybrid genome assembly - Nanopore and Illumina' developed by Melbourne Bioinformatics.

https://www.melbournebioinformatics.org.au/tutorials/tutorials/hybrid_assembly/nanopore_assembly/